

A SEVERE CASE OF TESTOTOXICOSIS IN AN INFANT DUE TO A C.1732G>C (P.ASP578HIS) LHCGR GENE MUTATION ASSOCIATED WITH NODULAR LEYDIG CELL HYPERPLASIA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Testotoxicosis is a rare gonadotropin-independent form of precocious puberty. Herein we discuss a uniquely severe case of severe testotoxicosis in infant male with a c.1732G>C (p.ASP578His) LHCGR gene mutation requiring surgical intervention.

Case Description: This 9-month-old male initially presented with extremely elevated levels of testosterone (1383 ng/dl) and undetectable ultrasensitive LH and FSH titers. On physical exam, he was Tanner stage 3. Scrotal ultrasound showed multiple bilateral nodular hypoechoic lesions. A genomic DNA 1732G>C mutation within the LHCGR gene leading to a p.Asp578His amino acid change was confirmed on genetic testing. Combination medical therapy with an androgen receptor blocker and aromatase inhibitor was initiated for testotoxicosis; however, his condition worsened on medical therapy with a further rise in testosterone levels (2177 ng/dl). He subsequently underwent two sequential orchiectomies for his condition with both pathologies demonstrating diffuse nodular Leydig cell hyperplasia.

Conclusions Herein we report the youngest case of medically refractory testotoxicosis associated with progressive bilateral diffuse nodular Leydig cell hyperplasia requiring aggressive surgical intervention. The germline c.1732G>C (p.ASP578His) mutation found in this case was previously described as somatic mutations in 3 boys with benign nodular adenoma of the testes.

KEYWORDS precocious puberty, lhcr, Leydig cell hyperplasia, testotoxicosis, refractory

Introduction

Testotoxicosis, or familial male-limited precocious puberty (FMPP), is a rare gonadotropin-independent form of precocious puberty. This is caused by constitutive activation of the Luteinizing

ing Hormone (LH) receptor and human Chorionic Gonadotropic Hormone receptor or LHCGR.[1]

The first case report of testotoxicosis described the condition in two brothers aged 2 and 3 years old.[2] The first genetic link found in eight different families with FMPP was a single base pair substitution of glycine for aspartate at position 578 (p.Asp578Gly) of the LHCG receptor. Furthermore, in COS-7 cell studies expressing the same mutant LH receptor, an increased cyclic AMP and testosterone production were observed, despite the absence of LH. Hence the aetiology of FMPP was elucidated to be due to autonomous Leydig cell activation.[3]

In a large study of 32 families with male-limited precocious puberty, a majority had a p.Asp578Gly mutation; however, other

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mutation in the same codon position such as p. Asp578Tyr was also described. As such, position 578 is considered a genetic hotspot for testotoxicosis.[4] On the contrary, inactivating mutations of the LHCGR gene in males is associated with Leydig cell agenesis or hypoplasia.[5]

On scrotal ultrasound, the testicles are characteristically heterogeneous with echogenic lesions that commonly represent a benign process.[6] Treatment is primarily medical therapy to inhibit the biosynthesis of sex steroids using either ketoconazole or an androgen receptor blockage coupled with inhibitor of estrogen production such as bicalutamide along with an aromatase inhibitor Anastrozole.[7] Herein we present a uniquely severe case of an infant boy with severe testotoxicosis refractory to medical therapy associated with progressive bilateral hypoechoic testicular lesions.

CASE REPORT

A 9-month-old male presented to the emergency room with a 2-month progressive history of penile enlargement, pubic hair development, body odour and prolonged penile erections. He was born at full term after a normal vaginal delivery. There was no significant family history of precocious puberty in any family members; although the family history was significant for retinoblastoma and osteosarcoma.

On initial examination, he appeared large for his age with coarse facial features and had a low-pitched voice. The scrotum appeared to be rugated and slightly enlarged with bilateral testicular volumes of 4 ml, along with pubic hair that was consistent with Tanner stage III. The penile stretch length was 6.5 cm with a circumference of 2.5 cm. Café au lait spots were not noted, and there were no neurological deficits.

Laboratory evaluation on presentation showed extremely elevated serum testosterone of 1383 ng/dl and only slightly elevated 17 OH-progesterone (OHP) levels of 507 ng/dl. On further endocrine laboratory analysis, he had undetectable beta-HCG and AFP levels along with undetectable ultrasensitive LH and FSH levels.

He underwent a Cortrosyn stimulation test, which excluded CAH (congenital adrenal hyperplasia). His elevated testosterone levels were independent of ACTH stimulation. The patient was diagnosed with testotoxicosis, and he was started on Bicalutamide (an androgen receptor blocker) at a dose of 25 mg daily in combination with Anastrozole (an aromatase inhibitor) 1mg daily.

Clinically, he continued to have prolonged erections along with the progression of secondary sex characteristics. The testosterone levels rose further up to 1542ng/dl. Testicular ultrasounds showed progressive heterogeneity of both testicles, as well as bilateral hypoechoic lesions and epididymal cysts. The largest hypoechoic lesion on the right testis increased from 2 mm to 10 mm within a 3-month period (Figure 1). Computed tomography of the chest and abdomen were negative for any masses or tumours, more specifically the adrenal glands were normal in shape and attenuation. Magnetic resonance imaging of the brain and pituitary gland were performed twice; once at the time of diagnosis and another at 18 months of age. Both studies showed normal brain structures without any abnormal enhancement or myelination.

At one year of age, he underwent an excisional biopsy of the right hypoechoic testicular lesion, which showed multiple nodules on frozen section and elements suspicious for seminoma. The patient underwent a right radical orchiectomy after a dis-

Fig.1. A longitudinal section of the right testicle on ultrasound. The right testicle is heterogenous with multiple hypoechoic lesions — the largest of these located on the lower pole of the right testicle.

cussion with the parents. The final pathology showed diffuse nodular Leydig cell hyperplasia. Genetic testing was performed at Athena diagnostics. A 1732G->C variation was found on the LHCGR gene resulting in a p.Asp578His amino acid change in both the testicular tissue and the patient's leukocytes. This was reported as pathogenic and associated with testotoxicosis.

After his right orchiectomy, while on the highest dose of Bicalutamide (50 mg daily) and Anastrozole 1mg daily, he continued to go through a growth spurt with a further rise in serum testosterone from 1990 ng/dl to 2177 ng/dl. His mother reported persistent nightly erections along with more pubic hair development and increases in his penile size. A follow-up testicular ultrasound on the remaining left testicle showed an increase in size to a volume of 2.7 cc. The left testicle started to become more heterogeneous in appearance with enlargement of the hypoechoic lesions.

Hemiskelton x-rays at ten months of age showed a bone age at the phalanges of 8 years. A repeat x-ray performed at 15 months showed a bone age at the phalanges of 9 years. The last determined bone age before publication of this case report was between 10-11 years at a chronological age of 2 years.

At 21 months of age, the patient continued to progress clinically with aggressive behaviour, painful erections, further development of secondary sex characteristics and elevations in testosterone levels. The patient has switched to Letrozole 2.5 mg, a more potent aromatase inhibitor, but was unable to tolerate it due to GI side effects. At this point, ketoconazole was proposed but was not initiated due to parental concerns of adrenal insufficiency. His testotoxicosis was now considered refractory to medical therapy. After a prolonged discussion with the parents regarding the risk of refractory testotoxicosis to his health versus the consequences of removing his remaining testicle, a decision was made to perform a left radical orchiectomy (Figure 2). After his bilateral orchiectomies, the patient's spontaneous erections resolved and his penile length decreased by 1.5 cm. However, he continues to show aggressive behaviour and retains a deep course voice. His testosterone level decreased to 2.8 ng/dl and is currently undetectable at <3 ng/dl.

DISCUSSION

Herein we present a severe case of gonadotropin-independent male precocious puberty, also called testotoxicosis, due to a

Fig.2. Left radical orchiectomy at 21 months of age: Photomicrograph shows the diffuse and nodular arrangement of Leydig cells with scattered, entrapped, and normal appearing seminiferous tubules. On higher power (insert) the cells are monomorphic, polygonal and medium-sized with abundant granular, eosinophilic cytoplasm. The nuclei are round with conspicuous nucleoli. Features that indicate malignancy such as marked nuclear and cytologic atypia, necrosis, lymphovascular invasion, increased mitotic rate and atypical mitosis are absent.[14]

c.1732G>C (p.ASP578His) LHCGR gene mutation. Patients with testotoxicosis have increased levels of testosterone along with low or suppressed LH and FSH levels, signifying an autonomous production of testosterone independent of trophic LH signalling.

Patients commonly present between 1 to 3 years of age with the development of secondary sexual characteristics such as pubic hair development, enlargement in penile length, as well as advancement in bone age and reduced adult height.[8] The size of the testis is usually prepubertal but can also be slightly enlarged due to enlargement of the epididymis. In almost all cases, medical management is the mainstay of therapy.

Traditionally, success has been reported with the use of the anti-fungal agent ketoconazole, which inhibits both adrenal and testicular steroid biosynthesis. However, it can also lower serum cortisol levels and can lead to adrenal insufficiency, as well as hepatic dysfunction.[9] Due to these adverse effects, ketoconazole is used less frequently. Recent reports using an androgen receptor blocker (Bicalutamide) and aromatase inhibitor (anastrozole) has been reported with good long-term success [7].

The c.1732G>C (p.ASP578His) LHCGR gene mutation in our case demonstrated a far more severe progression of the disease, while presenting at a significantly younger age than those previously reported by Liu et al.; who described the same mutation in 3 males with isosexual peripheral precocious puberty.[1] Liu et al. only found the mutation in the patients' testicular adenomas and not in the patients' leukocytes or the normal testicular tissues; implying that this was a somatic mutation. In our case, the same mutation was found in both his leukocytes and testicles (including normal testicular tissue), which is indicative of a germline mutation, and resulted in a more diffuse and severe clinical phenotype [1].

Furthermore, in the series by Liu et al., the chronological age of diagnosis was between 7.5 to 8.3 years with bone age advance-

ment ranging between 10-13 years. The maximum bone age advancement was 13 years in a 7.5-year-old boy. In our patient, his initial bone age was eight years at a chronological age of 10 months and progressed to 11 years when he was chronologically two years old. His latest bone age at the phalanges showed stability between 10-11 years. This gives him a predicted adult height of 4'4". Lastly, his peak testosterone level of 2177 ng/dl was 6 times higher than the peak testosterone level of 335 ng/dl reported by Liu et al.

Our case represents a uniquely severe form of testotoxicosis, which has not been previously reported. Firstly, the patient presented at approximately nine months of age, which to our best knowledge would be the youngest reported case. All previous cases presented at an age greater than one year.[10,11]

The patient was started on daily 25 mg of Bicalutamide and 1 mg of Anastrozole, which is effective in a majority of patients. However, our case progressed clinically with continued painful and prolonged erections, as well as the progression of secondary sex characteristics. The findings on scrotal ultrasound was another unique feature of this case, as it posed a significant Urologic dilemma. The patient was found to have diffuse bilateral heterogeneous testicles coupled with progressive enlargement of multiple hypoechoic lesions.

The initial challenge with the reported case was the presence of hypoechoic lesions on the right testicle, which is not commonly found in testotoxicosis associated LCH. Although an excisional biopsy was attempted in the initial treatment of the right testicle, the results of the frozen section were concerning for seminoma leading to a decision to perform a radical orchiectomy.

Testotoxicosis with associated Leydig cell hyperplasia (LCH) is often difficult to differentiate from Leydig cell tumour (LCT).[6,10,12] The ultrasonographic findings for testotoxicosis include testicular heterogeneity and intratesticular hyperechoic lesions. However, these features cannot be used in isolation to differentiate between LCH and LCT as such testicular tumour markers are commonly recommended as part of the initial evaluation. In our case, these were negative.

There are currently no universally accepted surgical guidelines for the management of LCH. Naughton et al. purposed an algorithm based on history, physical, tumour markers and ultrasound findings. In this algorithm, the presence of hypoechoic lesions on ultrasound, in the absence of positive tumour markers, dictated a radical orchiectomy.[6] However, a testis-sparing approach is preferred; and in the ten reported cases mentioned by Mennie et al., seven were treated with excisional biopsy ensuring clear margins versus three that were managed with radical orchiectomies.[10]

Martin et al. described an adult who was diagnosed as a child with testotoxicosis, who was later found to have a testicular seminoma at 35 years of age. This transformation to a testicular germ cell tumour was possibly linked to early and prolonged exposure to testosterone and aromatization to estradiol.[13]

A conservative approach was taken after the right radical orchiectomy; however, not only did the patient have clinical progression, he also had radiologic progression. The second unique surgical challenge of this case was the diffuse and bilateral nature of the disease, making a testis-sparing approach more difficult and less feasible on the remaining testicle.

The decision to perform an orchiectomy on the remaining testicle was made considering hormonal production and fertility versus the health-related risk associated with medically

Fig.3. Leydig cell clusters are found within tunica albuginea and paratesticular soft tissue. The Leydig cell clusters do not have atypia, mitosis or desmoplastic reaction in contrast with metastatic deposits.¹⁵ Leydig cells are often present in the paratesticular region¹⁶ and should not be interpreted as metastasis.

refractory testotoxicosis. Interestingly, the pathology reported not only confirmed the diagnosis of LCH but also identified local infiltration of Leydig cells into the paratesticular tissue and tunica albuginea owing to the severity of the disease (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION

Herein we presented a unique case of precocious puberty secondary to testotoxicosis from a germline c.1732G>C (p.ASP578His) LHCGR gene mutation. This case represents the youngest reported case of testotoxicosis at approximately nine months of age. Furthermore, this case was associated with progressive bilateral hypoechoic testicular on scrotal ultrasound, which is atypical of testotoxicosis (LCH). The patient failed medical therapy with an androgen receptor blocker (Bicalutamide) and aromatase inhibitor (Anastrozole), demonstrating both clinical and radiologic progression. The patient was successfully treated with subsequently bilateral orchiectomies at 1 and two years of age.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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